

RHIZOBACTERIA OF MILLET (*Panicum miliaceum*). ISOLATION AND STUDYING THEIR CERTAIN PROPERTIES.

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Abstract: In this study , plant growth-promoting bacteria (PGPR) were isolated from the rhizosphere of millet (*Panicum miliaceum*) and some of their morphological and physiological properties were studied. Currently, one of the priority areas of microbiology is the isolation, identification and application of highly active microorganisms. Such microorganisms are widely used in agriculture, the food industry and animal husbandry. Rhizobacteria, i.e. beneficial microorganisms living in the root zone of plants, are especially important for their properties that stimulate plant growth, improve their nutrition and protect against various diseases. The Gram reaction, catalase and oxidase activities, phosphate solubilization and siderophore production ability of the isolated isolates were evaluated. The results showed that the rhizosphere of millet is a source of beneficial microorganisms.

Keywords: Millet (*Panicum miliaceum*), rhizobacteria, nutrient medium (NA), KAA, GPA, PIKOVSKIY, Ashby, incubation, plant growth promoting bacteria , rhizosphere, PGPR, phosphate solubilization, siderophores

Introduction : For sustainable agriculture, it is important to introduce environmentally friendly alternatives to chemical fertilizers and pesticides. Plant Growth-Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR) living in the soil around plant roots play an important role in stimulating plant growth, improving nutrient uptake, producing phytohormones, and protecting against pathogens.

Millet (Panicum miliaceum) is a drought-resistant cereal crop widely cultivated in Central Asia. Therefore, isolating bacteria living in its rhizosphere and studying their biological properties serves as a scientific basis for the creation of biological fertilizers and biocontrol agents.

Research objective: The aim of this study is to isolate rhizobacteria from the rhizosphere and root surface of millet (*Panicum miliaceum*), study their morphological, physiological, and biochemical properties, and determine the potential of these bacteria to stimulate and protect plant growth in saline soil .

Materials and methods :

Sampling : Rhizosphere soil samples were collected from healthy *Panicum miliaceum* plants during the growing season. The soil adhering to the roots was collected under sterile conditions and brought to the laboratory.

Isolation of rhizobacteria : 1g of soil was placed in 9 ml of sterile 0.85% NaCl solution and serially diluted to 10^{-1} – 10^{-6} . 0.1 ml of each dilution was taken and plated on Nutrient agar, (NA), KAA, GPA and Ashby media and incubated at 28 - 30 °C for 24–72 hours.

Morphological and biochemical characteristics :

The isolated colonies were brought into pure culture and studied for the following:

- Colony shape, color, size ; - Gram stain result ; - Catalase and oxidase tests .

Functional tests : Isolates were tested for the following properties:

- Phosphate dissolution (on Pikovskaya medium) ; - Siderophore production (CAS-agar test)

Results : A total of 18 pure bacterial isolates were isolated from the rhizosphere of millet. Of these,; 11 were Gram-negative and 7 were Gram-positive bacteria.

61% of the isolates exhibited catalase activity, 45% had phosphate solubilizing ability (Graph 1); 34% siderophore production (Figure 2) . The colonies were of different colors, shapes and sizes, and differed in growth rate and adaptability to the environment. The results indicate the presence of potentially useful microorganisms as PGPR.

Graph 1: Phosphorus assimilation activity of rhizosphere bacteria in Pikovsky nutrient medium.

Graph 2: Siderophore activity by Cas test.

Discussion : In saline and arid soils of the Aral Sea region, rhizosphere microflora is one of the main ecological supporting factors for plants. The results confirm that the millet rhizosphere is a biologically active environment. Phosphate-solubilizing and siderophore-producing bacteria help the plant to better absorb minerals. This increases the stress resistance and yield of crops. The results were previously reported in other is consistent with the PGPR activity observed in the rhizosphere of crops, indicating that the growth-promoting and protective properties of rhizobacteria are widespread and that their application as biological fertilizers is promising.

The change in color from blue to yellow or orange in the CAS test is associated with the release of Fe^{3+} ions by siderophores, and the results of this test allow an objective assessment of the metabolic activity of the isolates. The different production levels obtained in the study results may be related to the genetic characteristics of the bacteria, living conditions in the rhizosphere, and salt tolerance mechanisms. It is possible that the high mineralization level of the Aral Sea soils acts as a stress factor that enhances siderophore production.

The isolated bacteria can also be tested with crops in saline soil in the future and studied as biocontrol agents.

Conclusion :

The study showed that the isolated rhizobacteria can play an important role in stimulating the growth of *Panicum miliaceum* in saline soils and protecting

plants from stress factors. In the future, these isolates can be further studied through molecular genetic analysis and used in agricultural practice as biopreparations. At the same time, the results obtained also indicate the possibilities of increasing crop productivity and developing environmentally friendly biotechnological approaches.

of millet (*Panicum miliaceum*) have been found to have beneficial properties that stimulate plant growth, confirming their potential for the production of biological fertilizers and bioprotection agents in the future.

Overall, the results obtained indicate that the siderophore-producing potential of rhizobacteria found in the Aral Sea region is quite high. These isolates provide an important scientific basis for further selection as biofertilizers or plant growth-promoting microorganisms (PGPR). The possibility of using such bacteria in bioremediation of saline soils is also a promising direction.

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